

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PREPARING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION

Khasanova Irodaxon Najmiddin kizi

Doctoral student at Namangan State University

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Annotation: In this article, the educational traditions and beliefs, methods and guidelines inherited from our ancestors are theoretically analyzed. The theoretical foundations of "Pedagogy of preschool education" are aimed at raising the mental maturity of a person, the national foundations of preschool pedagogy are based on the principles of national heritage and universal human values, the development of the child's consciousness.

Key words: Preschool educational institution, manual, personnel training, pedagogical technology

The upbringing of a person as perfect in all respects is a long-standing dream of our people, and our ancestors were constantly looking for ways, rules of law to teach enlightenment, spirituality and culture to the younger generation, to lead them to perfection. And this was the reason for the coming to the field of pedagogical science. The achievement of a person of enlightenment and spiritual perfection is carried out in the leadership of pedagogical science.

The study of the laws of upbringing as mature in all respects from the moment the child is born, until he goes to school, is the subject of preschool pedagogy. He developed the unity of educational influence of preschool institutions and the family, involvement in the work of a preschool educational institution and school, the preparation of children for schooling, the tasks, principles, content, methods, forms of educational and educational work in the conditions of social preschool education and its organization. Pedagogy of preschool education was formed as an integral part of it in the system of Pedagogical Sciences.

Three thousand years ago, in the Holy Book of the Zoroastrian religion "Avesto", schools were established under its temples, and a system of education and education of children was developed by the priests. This educational and educational system was implemented in the following order: religious and moral education, physical education, teaching to read and write.

Our ancestors azal have long paid special attention to the upbringing of a child. Imam Al-Bukhari, Jesus at-Termizi, Abu Rayhon Beruni, Az-Zamakhshari, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulhamid Chulpan, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Alisher Navoi, great alimu Adib, fazilu-fuzalar have finished many works on education. This is evidenced by such works as the "city of Fazil people" by the founders of Oriental pedagogy Abu Nasr Farabi, the work "Qutadgil bilig" by Yusuf Khos Hajib, "Mahbub ul-kulub" by Alisher Navoi, "Qabusnoma" by Kaikovus.

In the development of pedagogy as a science, the contribution of the Czech pedagogue, scientist Ian Amos Komensky (1592-1670) was great. His work "great didactics" is rightfully considered the first scientific work created in the field of pedagogy. In addition to him, the pre-school instruction manual "School of mothers" and several books are noteworthy. In his pedagogical theory, Komensky puts forward the concept of the harmony of upbringing with

nature. When raising a child, the educator says that the gardener is obliged to take into account the natural cognitive properties of the tree in it, as he takes into account the law of biological growth. Komensky assures that everyone will be involved in the study, everyone should receive general education.

Since the years of independence, the head of state has also been encouraged to reflect on preschool education, even until the adoption of the law "on education", the "national program of training". And today we are approaching this issue in a new way. After all, according to the requirements of the program, the type of preschool education - along with the preparation of the child for school, ensures his growth in a healthy state, prepares him for regular education, instills in him a sense of desire to study. In subsequent years, a new network of preschool institutions is being formed. As an example, the number of non-state preschool institutions, short-term preschool institutions, groups teaching children choreography, fine and musical art, computer literacy is increasing every day. All this creates a charter for the upbringing of our preschool children on the basis of the requirements of the "National Personnel Training Program". Preschool education ensures that the child is healthy, comprehensively developed and formed, instills in him a sense of desire to study, prepares him for regular education.

Preschool education is carried out in state and non-state preschool institutions and families until the child reaches the age of 6-7 years. Neighborhoods, public and charitable organizations, international foundations are actively involved in the realization of the goals and objectives of preschool education. For the development of preschool education, it will be necessary to carry out:

- Priority training of qualified educator and pedagogical personnel;
- Search and introduction of effective psychological and pedagogical methods of preschool education;
- Organizational, psychological, pedagogical and methodological support of the upbringing of children in the family;
- Creation and production of modern educational and methodical manuals, technical means, toys and games;
- Creation of conditions for the spiritual education of preschool children on the basis of the rich cultural heritage of the people and universal values;
- Selection of alternative programs for different types of preschool institutions, the possibility of providing qualified advice on all issues;
- Development of technologies for the support and development of a network of preschool educational and health-improving institutions.

Education and upbringing of preschool children largely depends on the provision of education with programs that respond to the characteristics of the child's psyche in preschool age, methodological recommendations, instructional teaching aids. In this, the main educational manual used in education is manuals that ensure the orientation of the interaction of a child and an adult to a person (notebook for separate work, albums, flemaster, pen, paints, etc.).k) The created software and methodological complex should provide the standard of preschool education, the main directions in working with children and their development. This complex provides for the creation of textbooks and manuals for a new generation of educators and other specialists. Also, in the educational and educational

process, an idea is made on the theoretical and practical aspects of the subject game, which develop from the methods of organizing gaming activities.

The use of pedagogical technologies in preschool education is intended for a certain scientific design that strictly requires educational goals and evaluates the accuracy of stage changes and the results obtained. Modern developmental pedagogical technologies are directed not only to the educational process, but also to the psychological processes of the child, his personal qualities, mental and creative abilities, physical development, in the conditions of humanism of Education, pedagogical technologies are seen in the relationship of serious acceptance of the child from the pedagogical. The effectiveness of these is diagnosed when pedagogical technologies are used in pedagogical processes. This ensures that the child reacts openly to the educational impact.

The implementation of the algorithm for managing the effectiveness of preschool education, that is, the systematic rules of observation, the set educational and educational goals, is determined by observing and correcting the activities of children's admission, the above testifies to the fact that before the preschool education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the individual characteristics of the child..

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